

MRI Reconstruction Using Singular Value Decomposition

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Abstract - This work proposes the application of the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) technique to reduce noise and perform compression in magnetic resonance images (MRI) of the skull region. The results demonstrate that reducing the rank aiming at storage compression can favor both storage space and the preservation of essential information in the image. However, a drastic reduction in rank can lead to a significant degradation in the quality of the reconstructed image, evidenced by an increase in the Mean Squared Error (MSE).

Keywords: Magnetic Resonance Image, Singular Value Decomposition, Compression, Reconstruction, Noise.

INTRODUCTION

Biomedical imaging is widely used in digital signal processing for analysis and diagnosis of medical conditions. Digital signal processing applied to biomedical images can involve techniques such as filtering (1), (2), segmentation (3), registration and reconstruction of three-dimensional images (4), (5), allowing the extraction of useful information and the detection of anomalies or pathologies

In image processing, Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) can be used to compress images, as well as to improve their quality. Image compression with SVD is performed by reducing the number of singular values, which allows the reduction of the original matrix dimension, reducing the image file size. On the other hand, quality improvements can be achieved by reconstructing the image using a larger number of singular values. This allows the removal of noise or imperfections from the original image, improving its final quality.

In the work presented by (6), which addresses the reconstruction of magnetic resonance images using the SVD method, it estimates the approximation of the lowest rank based on the Akaike Information Criterion. The authors evaluate the performance of the results through signal-to-noise analysis and other metrics such as compression range and mean squared error.

In (7), as well as in (6), SVD is used and the rank is estimated for the matrix reconstruction process. The authors of (7) also evaluate the noise reduction performance with the contribution of the *Non-Local Means* (NLM) filter. The authors' main objective is based on reducing noise in HARDI data (High Angular Resolution Diffusion Imaging) to obtain better field constructions depending on the distribution of orientations in the images.

A framework to reduce noise through the combination of stabilizing variance transformation and Gaussian technique applied to data is developed in (8). The work addresses the analysis of the signal-to-noise ratio, as in (6).

The work (9) uses K-Means-SVD technique, Simple Linear Interaction Clustering, fusion optimization algorithm and the profuse clustering technique to reduce noise in lung cancer CT images. The authors aim to make diagnostic decisions more accurate through the noise reduction method. The results demonstrate significant noise reduction and satisfactory performance even at SNR levels of 60 dB.

The objective of this work is to apply Singular Value

Decomposition to magnetic resonance images and evaluate the results of image reconstruction. This article is organized as follows: Introduction that presents the main concepts and approaches used in the state of the art. Next, the Methodology on which this article was based is presented. Sequentially, there are the Results obtained and the discussions. And finally, the Conclusion.

METHODOLOGY

In this work, a magnetic resonance image dataset (IMR) is used from (10). The set of images refers to the region of the brain with the aim of reducing the noise present in the images through Singular Value Decomposition. In Figure 1 we can visualize the magnetic resonance image used to generate the approach proposed in this work.

Figure 1. Magnetic Resonance Imaging of Skull (brain region)

The following definitions are considered for the correct understanding of the equations presented in this work:

Singular value decomposition represents a significant topic in linear algebra and data analysis. This technique consists of decomposing the matrix A , which has dimension $m \times n$, into 3 other matrices, namely: U , Σ and V , as in the Equation 1:

$$A = U\Sigma V \quad (1)$$

U and V being orthogonal matrices; U is called the left-hand singular value matrix, Σ represents the diagonal

Figure 2. Result of image reconstruction from different rank values; (a) $k = 20$, (b) $k = 40$, (c) $k = 60$, (d) $k = 80$, (e) $k = 100$ and (f) $k = 111$

matrix and the V matrix is called the right-hand eigenvalue matrix.

The Σ matrix is formed by singular values originating from the original matrix. The singular values are obtained from the square root of the eigenvalues of the original matrix multiplied by themselves.

In the matrix U , the singular vectors are calculated by multiplying the eigenvalues of the original data and the matrix of singular values.

And the eigenvalue matrix on the right, V , is formed by multiplying the eigenvectors of the original transposed matrix and the singular values. Such a matrix is composed of columns that form an orthogonal basis for the column space of the original matrix.

By choosing a smaller number of singular values, it is possible to reduce the storage space of the reconstructed matrix, resulting in image compression. However, the drastic reduction in the number of singular values can cause the loss of relevant information, as well as reducing the quality of the reconstructed image. The calculation of the storage space of the A_k matrix (reconstructed image) is defined using the Equation 2:

$$k \cdot (m + n + 1) \quad (2)$$

The compression range is an important measure of image quality, as images with smaller compression ranges tend to have higher quality, while larger compression ranges can result in images with loss of information and less sharpness.

The compression range for A_k is calculated by the Equation 3:

$$C_r = \frac{m \cdot n}{k \cdot (m + n + 1)} \quad (3)$$

The mean squared error (MSE) is a metric commonly used to measure the difference between an original image and a compressed image. To analyze the quality of the reconstructed image, the mean squared error is used, according to the following Equation 4, where x and y are the coordinates of the pixels in the image.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{m \cdot n} \sum_{y=1}^m \sum_{x=1}^n (f_A(x, y) - f_{A_k}(x, y)) \quad (4)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the Figure 2, it is possible to observe the image reconstruction for different rank values, ranging from $k = 20$ to $k = 111$. This variation in the number of singular values significantly influences the quality of the reconstructed image.

By reducing the value of k , the amount of information retained in the reconstructed matrix A_k decreases, leading to storage compression. This can be advantageous in terms of saving space, which is crucial in image storage and transmission applications. However, this space saving comes at a cost, as a drastic reduction in k can result in the loss of relevant information and degradation of the quality of the reconstructed image.

Table 1 presents a more detailed analysis of the results for different values of k . The *Storage(bytes)* column shows the amount of storage space required to represent the A_k matrix, while the C_r column (compression range) indicates the relative size reduction compared to the original image. The column *MSE*, quantifies the difference between the original image and the reconstructed image. It is observed that as k decreases, the storage and compression range increase, but the *MSE* also increases, indicating a degradation in the quality of the reconstructed image.

Table 1. Comparison of occupied space metrics in bytes, compression range and mean squared error in values of the A_k matrix.

k	Storage (bytes)	C_r	MSE
20	9040	5.5586	185.4378
40	18080	2.7793	69.5999
60	27120	1.8529	27.0487
80	36160	1.3896	10.9176
100	45200	1.1117	4.1039
Original	50172	1	

Figure 3. Graph of the arrangement of the eigenvalues (y-axis) of the matrix Σ . and rank values (x-axis)

It is crucial to note that the quality of image reconstruction depends not only on k , but also on the characteristics of the original image. Furthermore, the graph in Figure 3 presents the arrangement of the eigenvalues of the Σ matrix, which can be useful for understanding how information is distributed and quantified in the main components during the SVD process.

Choosing the value of k is a compromise between space savings and image quality. Since reducing k can save storage space, it can also lead to significant losses in the quality of the reconstructed image. Therefore, it is essential to consider the specific needs of the task when choosing the appropriate post value.

CONCLUSION

The study analyzed the effects of variation in the number of singular values (rank) in image reconstruction, evaluating the relationship between space savings and image quality. The results revealed that rank reduction, aimed at storage compression, can favor both storage space and the preservation of essential information in the image. However, a drastic reduction in rank can lead to a significant degradation in the quality of the reconstructed image, as evidenced by the increase in the Mean Square Error. The comparative analysis also highlighted the importance of carefully choosing the k value based on the specific needs of the problem. Furthermore, the study provided useful information about the distribution of eigenvalues in the singular matrix, contributing to a deeper understanding of the image reconstruction process using SVD.

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